

NURSING INTERVENTION FOR APPLICATION OF SAFETY MEASURES FOR CHILDREN UNDERGOING HEMODIALYSIS

ENAAM EL METWALLY MOHAMED MOHAMED

M.Sc Nursing, Ain Shams University, Governorate, Egypt. *Corresponding Author

EMAN AMIN MOHAMED

Professor, Pediatric Nursing, Faculty of Nursing - Ain Shams University, Governorate, Egypt.

BOTHAYNA NADER SADEK

Assistant Professor, Pediatric Nursing, Faculty of Nursing - Ain Shams University, Governorate, Egypt.

Abstract

Background: Hemodialysis is the most common method used to treat advanced and permanent kidney failure in pediatric patients. Hemodialysis defined as a medical procedure that uses a special machine to filter waste products from the blood safety measures. **Aim:** The study is aimed to evaluate the effect of application of nursing intervention for safety measures on nurses' performance for care of children undergoing hemodialysis. . **Setting:** This study was conducted at hemodialysis units affiliated to both Mansoura University Children Hospital and Ain Shams University Hospital. **Sampling:** This study encompasses A purposive sample of 80 nurses who are qualified is providing direct care for children undergoing hemodialysis. A quasi experimental research design was selected. **Tool I:** An Interview Questionnaire format was used (pre/post intervention) to assess Nurses' knowledge regarding hemodialysis care and preparation for Children Undergoing Hemodialysis and Safety measures for Children. **Tool II:** Observational Checklist Sheets for application of safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis. **Results:** More than two thirds (68.8%) of studied nurse had satisfactory knowledge about the hemodialysis at post intervention compared to 6.3% of them pre intervention. Mostly (81.2%) of the studied nurses had competent total practice post implementation of training program in compared to only (8.8%) pre implementation. **Conclusion:** There were strong positive correlation between the studied nurses' total knowledge and their total practice about safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis post intervention at $r = .590$ ($p < 0.01$). **Recommendation:** Periodic training programs and refreshing courses should be provided to nurses to enhance the use safety measures, which will reflect into their performance and minimize the risk for transmission of infection.

Keywords: Nursing Intervention, Safety Measures, Children Undergoing Hemodialysis

INTRODUCTION

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is defined as the presence of kidney damage or an estimated glomerular filtration rate (EGFR) less than 60 ml/min/1.73 mt², persisting for 3 months or more, irrespective of the cause. It is a state of progressive loss of kidney function ultimately resulting in the need for renal replacement therapy (dialysis or transplantation). Kidney damage refers to pathologic abnormalities either suggested by imaging studies or renal biopsy, abnormalities in urinary sediment, or increased urinary albumin excretion rates (Alzamanan et al., 2018).

The prevalence of pediatric chronic kidney disease (CKD) ranges from 15 to 74.7 cases per 1 million children. Mortality among children who progress to end-stage kidney disease (ESKD) is 30 to 50 times higher compared to that in the general population. Such a wide range in the prevalence of CKD was

caused by the lack of agreement on the unified diagnostic and classification system for CKD for a long time (**Masalskienė et al., 2021**).

Kidney disease in children can be caused by birth defects, hereditary diseases, infection, nephrotic syndrome, systemic diseases, trauma and urine blockage or reflux. From birth to age 4, birth defects and hereditary diseases are the leading causes of kidney failure. Between ages 5 and 14, kidney failure is most commonly caused by hereditary diseases, nephrotic syndrome, and systemic diseases. Between ages 15 and 19, diseases that affect the glomeruli are the leading cause of kidney failure, and hereditary diseases become less common (**Okada, 2020**).

Chronic peritoneal dialysis (CPD) is the most common dialysis treatment modality used to treat pediatric children with end-stage kidney disease (ESKD), particularly in children less than five years of age. Peritoneal dialysis (PD) is a safe, simple and inexpensive procedure. PD can provide adequate clearance, ultrafiltration and correction of metabolic abnormalities even in those who are critically ill. It is also a useful modality in newborns, including babies weighing <1000 g and infants in whom obtaining a vascular access for extracorporeal therapy can be very challenging (**Aziz & Chaudhary, 2021**).

The safety measures for hemodialysis vascular access including initiation of hemodialysis and identification of child and his machine, hemodialysis facilities, equipment and disposables, water treatment stations and monitoring hemodialysis membranes and fluxes, hemodialysis time and frequency, implementing hemodialysis filtration (HDF) in HD units. HD dose quantification, blood pressure control, guidelines safety measures for hemodynamic instability during HD, standard operating procedures for the management of a child with hemodialysis care, safety measures guidelines on nutrition for child on maintenance hemodialysis, clinical performance management and infection control policy all of this safety measures for improving in health care outcome for dialysis children (**Supreme Council of University Hospitals Hemodialysis Guidelines, 2019**); assess the fistula/graft and graft and arm before, after each dialysis or every shift the access flow, complications assess the complication of central venous catheter, tip placement, exit site complications document and notify appropriate health care provider regarding any concerns (**Agarwal et al., 2019**).

The dialysis nurse plays a vital role in controlling infections, providing information, care, support, understanding and therapeutic counseling to the pediatric patient and his family throughout the entire illness. The nursing management must be provided in order to reducing the complications of renal function and the stresses of dealing with a life threatening illness (**Al-Mawsheki et al., 2016**).

Significance of the Study:

Pediatric patient's safety is a main goal in any treatment protocol and a central concern of current health-care delivery systems World Health Organization (**WHO, 2018**). So, over the past several years, pediatric patients safety has become a key priority for health systems. However, despite increased awareness, harm to pediatric patients safety is still common and has not shown a significant decline (**Nehus, & Mitsnefes (2019)**).

Improving in health care outcomes for hemodialysis of pediatrics, continuous improving program. Promoting high quantity service in treating pediatric on hemodialysis. A guide for improving and monitoring pediatrics patient having hemodialysis safety measures the quality of nursing care is influenced by the knowledge judgment. Skills and values of those participating in the care of pediatrics patients having hemodialysis and the nurses' cognitive ability to decide on a plan of action that depends upon that education. Therefore, the nursing action begins with nurses' knowledge pilot study and skills intervention. Service educational program is a method for teaching nurses which is designed and constructed for the independent education an attempt to avoid any strains for acquired new

information at any time and to remove any barriers which may prevent the nurses from introducing for training the educational program have a positive effect of the nurses' knowledge and performance and improved the quality of nursing care given to pediatrics having hemodialysis. So that, there is a great interest to conduct such type of research, which might assist nurses to safety and effectively offer care to those critical hemodialysis pediatric patient.

Aim of the study:

This study aims to evaluate the effect of application of nursing intervention for safety measures on nurses' performance for care of children undergoing hemodialysis.

Research Hypothesis:

The application of safety measures will affect positively nurse's performance for caring of children undergoing hemodialysis.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS

Research design: A quasi experimental research design was utilized.

Setting: The study was conducted at **hemodialysis Unit in** El Demerdash Hospital, Ain Shams University, because it received clients from different socio demographic status, and highly population rate.

Sample: A purposive sample of nurses (n=80) who are qualified is providing direct care for children undergoing hemodialysis in the previously mentioned study setting. Hemodialysis Unit (46 nurses) at Hemodialysis unit in Mansoura University Hospital and Ain Shams Pediatric Hemodialysis Unit composed of (34 nurses) under the following inclusion criteria: 1- Nurses who are qualified in direct care for children undergoing hemodialysis. 2- Nurses who have more than 1 year of experience. Exclusion criteria: New graduated nurses, employed nurses, and head nurse.

Tools of data collection: Data were collected through the use of the following tools:

Tool I: An Interview Questionnaire format was used (pre/post intervention) that was designed by the researcher after reviewing related literatures; it was in an Arabic Language in form of open and close ended questions to gather data in relation to:

Part I: Characteristics of nurses such as age, gender, marital status, qualification, years of experience, Experience years in hemodialysis and Training program in Hemodialysis.

Part II: Nurses' knowledge regarding nursing intervention for application of safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis used Pre and Post Intervention were and included the following:

- a) Nurses' knowledge regarding hemodialysis as regards: concept, indication, and complication
- b) Nurses' knowledge regarding care and preparation for Children Undergoing Hemodialysis was used before, during and after session.
- c) Nurses' Knowledge about Safety measures for Children Undergoing Hemodialysis regarding concept, Importance of safety measures for Children and Types of safety measures.
- d) Nurses Knowledge about Steps of preparation for Children Undergoing Hemodialysis were included 21 questions, injecting heparin in haemodialysis catheter, needs for dealing with the haemodialysis catheter, causes of increase children's temperature during the haemodialysis session, Time of take blood sample of kidney functions and others for haemodialysis children, Uses of high filtration for haemodialysis more than 6 hours per session.

According to the child weight, Duration of haemodialysis, measuring the haemodialysis dose at least monthly, measuring the blood pressure during the haemodialysis session, Proper action for hemodialysis children suffered from hypotension. The **Scoring:** Nurses' knowledge was checked with a model key answer and accordingly their knowledge were considered either complete =1 mark or incomplete = 0. The total score of knowledge were classified As Satisfactory: > 80% of total knowledge score while Unsatisfactory: < 80 of total knowledge score.

Tool II: Observational Checklist Sheets were used for application of safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis. It was adapted from **Supreme Council of University Hospitals Hemodialysis Guidelines (2019)** to assess nurses' performance regarding application of guidelines for management of children was used Pre and Post Intervention program included the following questions: Preparation of the children contains (6) questions, Preparation of the hemodialysis machine, included (6) questions, Hemodialysis membrane and fluxes included (2) question, Intradialytic patient's assessment and hemodialysis machine monitoring included (8) questions Hemodialysis time and frequency were included (2) questions, Implementing hemodialysis filtration in hemodialysis unit included (2), Hemodialysis dose quantification included (4) questions. Guidelines safety measures for hemodynamic in stability during hemodialysis, included 4, hemodialysis dose quantification included, managing suboptimal dialysis adequacy included (12) questions, blood pressure control included (7) questions, Termination of procedure as regards children included (12) questions, Termination of procedure as regards machine included (3) questions Hemodialysis Dose Quantification included (4) questions Nursing guidelines for children who experienced long recovery time more than 6 hours included (5) questions Standard operating procedures for the management of a child hemodialysis care, Safety measure guidelines on nutrition included 38 questions. Policy of infection control, included (13) questions.

The Scoring: As regards nurses' total performance, nurses were directly observed using the observational checklists and accordingly their practices were each correctly done =1, incorrectly or not done= 0, the total scoring for nurses practices were considered as the following the Competent: >90% of total performance score and Incompetent: < 90% of total performance score.

2. Operational Design:

The operational design was included; preparatory phase, ethical considerations, tools validity and reliability, pilot study and field of work.

Preparatory phase:

The researcher reviewed the local and international literature to be aware of various aspects of the research problem, by using books, journals and internet search and to design the study tools.

Tool validity and reliability:

Tools of data collection were investigated for their content validity by three experts of two professions in pediatric nursing and one profession in medical and surgical nursing. The experts reviewed the content of the instruments and to judge its clarity, relevance, comprehensiveness, simplicity and applicability. This phase took around one month (April 2021) and there was no change in tools at the end of this phase except arrangement of some questions in the questionnaire sheet.

Testing reliability of proposed tool was done using the Chronbach's Alpha coefficient test to measure the internal consistency of the tools. It was found that

	Apha	No of item
Knowledge	0.843	30
Practices	.990	128

Ethical Considerations:

The researcher explained the aim, nature and expected outcomes of the study to the studied nurses before their participation in order to obtain their acceptance. The nurses were informed that, the study was harmless and all the gathered data were confidential and used for the research purposive only. The studied nurse's participant in the study was voluntary and studied nurses were informed that, they had the right to withdrawal at any time from the study.

Pilot Study:

A pilot study was carried out involving 10% (n=6) nurses to test clearness and applicability of the study tools and to assess the time required for fulfilling the tools. No radical modifications were done according to the results of pilot study. Studied nurses involved in the pilot study were included in the study sample. This phase took around one month (May 2021).

Field of Work:

The following phases were adopted to achieve the aim of the current study; assessment, planning, implementation and evaluation phases. These phases were conveyed from the earliest starting point of June 2022 to the end of November 2022 covering 6 months.

Assessment Phase:

This phase included interviews with studied nurses to collect the data. The researcher was available 4 days/week; (Saturday, Monday, Tuesday, and Wednesday) two days for each hospital, during morning shift (from 8.00 am to 1pm hour). Data was obtained from average number 5-6 nurses per/day. At the beginning of interview; the researcher welcomed each nurse, introduce herself, explained the purpose, activities and duration of the study. Then, pre-test was done using the tools of the study. The time required for finishing each tool was around (30-45 minutes).

Planning Phase:

Based on data obtained from pre-test assessment and relevant review of literature, the intervention program was developed by the researcher.

General Objective of the Nursing Intervention Program:

The nursing intervention aimed to evaluate the effect of application of safety measures intervention on nurses' performance for care of children undergoing hemodialysis.

Specific Objectives:

At the end of nursing intervention sessions, the nurses in hemodialysis will be able to:

- Identify the concept, indication, complication of hemodialysis, and safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis
- Explain the application of safety measure and its objectives
- Recognize the steps of preparation for children undergoing hemodialysis.
- Describe proper procedure for hemodialysis suffered from fistula edema during the session
- Demonstrate the preparation of the hemodialysis machine
- Demonstrate dose quantification and to managing suboptimal dialysis adequacy
- Demonstrate termination of procedure for children and machine

- Demonstrate nursing guidelines for children who experienced long recovery time more than 6 hours
- Perform the proper types of nutrition maintenance for children undergoing hemodialysis
- Demonstrate the technique of maintain and apply policy of infection control standard precautions for children undergoing hemodialysis

Implementation phase:

Firstly, the nurses were informed about the time and place of sessions that were conducted at the Hemodialysis units. Program was implemented through sessions. The studied nurses were divided into 10 groups each group consisted of 5-6 nurses, the program intervention has taken 10 sessions for each group, distributed as the following; (4) sessions for theoretical part and (6) session for practices part, at the same time of each session was ranged between 30 to 45 minutes. The researcher was available 4 days/week in two hospitals; the time of session conduction was determined nurses' readiness.

From here, the sessions were repeated to each subgroup of nurses. As regards the theoretical part, it was classified as the following; the first session (time consumed: 30 minute) of nursing intervention involved introduction and obtains an overview about application of safety measure and its objectives. Second session, involved knowledge regarding hemodialysis for children undergoing hemodialysis. Third session, included knowledge about steps of preparation for children undergoing hemodialysis. Fourth session knowledge about steps of preparation for children undergoing hemodialysis

Concerning practical part, it was classified as the following: First session (time consumed: 30 minutes) involved nurses' performance regarding application of guidelines for children undergoing hemodialysis. Second session involved nurses' performance regarding dose quantification and managing suboptimal dialysis for children undergoing hemodialysis. Third session: involved nurses' performance after session of hemodialysis for children undergoing hemodialysis. Fourth session: nurses' performance regarding maintain nursing guidelines for children who experienced long recovery for children undergoing hemodialysis. Fifth session: nurses' performance regarding proper maintain nutrition for children undergoing hemodialysis, sixth session: nurses' performance regarding maintain and apply policy of infection control standard precautions for children undergoing hemodialysis.

Teaching strategies & teaching methods and media are:

- 1) Educational session about hemodialysis and safety measure guidelines.
- 2) Training session including teaching and learning methods that was lecture, video film, PowerPoint, booklet, group discussion, brain storming, flipchart and posters.

D- Evaluation Phase:

Upon the completion and implementation of the program, the post test was obtained for nurses to evaluate the outcomes of the nursing intervention program using the same preprogram tools by using the same pretest format.

III- Administrative Design:

An official letter approval was obtained from the Dean of Faculty of Nursing, Ain Shams University, administrators and head of units of the previously mentioned settings to obtained their approval and cooperation which is needed for charring out this study. A clear explanation was given about the nature, importance and expected outcomes of the study.

IV-Statistical Analysis:

Data was presented in tables and graphs as number and percentage calculation with suitable significant test. The data was collected, coded, and entered into a personal computer. It was analyzed with the program statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 22. Data were presented using descriptive statistics in the form of frequencies and percentages, description of quantitative variable as mean, SD, and range, description of qualitative variables as numbers and percentages and Chi-square test was used to compare qualitative variable, R-test was used to compare quantitative variables in the same group and correlation coefficient test was used to rank different variables against each other either positively or inversely. Statistical insignificance was considered at $P>0.05$ and significance at $P<0.05$.

RESULTS

Table (1): Number and percentage distribution of studied nurses' characteristics (n= 80)

Demographic Characteristics	No	%
Age/ years		
20-<30	29	36.2
30-<40	24	30.0
40-<50	26	32.5
≥50	1	1.3
Mean and SD	31.49±4.621	
Gender		
Male	21	26.2
Female	59	73.8
Marital status		
Single	24	30.0
Married	43	53.7
Divorced	5	6.3
Widowed	8	10.0
Qualification		
Diploma	8	10.0
Specialized diploma	3	3.7
Nursing institute	29	36.3
Bachelor	37	46.3
Postgraduate	3	3.7
Year's of Experience		
<5	18	22.5
5-<10	17	21.2
10-<15	36	45.0
≥15	9	11.3
Mean and SD	11.63±4.12	
Experience years in hemodialysis		
<one	19	23.7
1-<5	21	26.3
5- <10	32	40.0
≥10	8	10.0
Mean and SD	9.36±4.12	
Training program in Hemodialysis		
Yes	78	97.5
No	2	2.5

Table (1): showed that, nearly one third (36.2%) of studied nurses their age ranging between 20 to < 30 years with the mean age 31.49 ± 4.621 years. Moreover, less than three quarters (73.8%) of them were female, more than half (53.7%) of them were married. Also, less and more than two fifths (36.3% and 46.3%) of them had technical nursing institutes and had bachelor degree respectively. Regarding years of experience of studied nurses 45% were ranging between 10 to <15 years with the mean 11.63 ± 4.12 , and 40% of them had years of experience from 5 < 10 years in hemodialysis. Additionally, the most (97.5%) of them had training intervention in hemodialysis.

Table (2): Number and percentage distribution of studied nurses background Knowledge regarding hemodialysis Pre and Post Intervention (n=80)

Knowledge	Pre intervention		Post Intervention		Statistical test	
	N	%	N	%	χ^2	Sig
Concept of haemodialysis						
Incorrect	52	65.0	2	2.5	69.88	0.000**
Correct	28	35.0	78	97.5		
Indications of haemodialysis						
Incorrect	78	97.5	18	22.5	93.75	0.000**
Correct	2	2.5	62	77.5		
Complications of haemodialysis						
Incorrect	71	88.7	12	15.0	87.14	0.000**
Correct	9	11.3	68	85.0		

**** Statistical significance difference**

Table (2) reveals that there was a statistically significant difference between pre and post intervention among studied nurses' knowledge regarding hemodialysis, the most (97.5%) of studied nurse had correct answer among definition of hemodialysis at post intervention compared to more than one third (35%) of them at pre intervention. Concerning indication of hemodialysis more than three quarter (77.5%) of them had correct answer at post intervention compared to (2.5%) of them at pre intervention. In addition, the majority (85%) of the studied nurses had correct answer at post intervention compared to (11.3%) of them at pre intervention.

Figure (1): Percentage distribution of studied nurses according to total knowledge about application of safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis pre and post intervention (n=80)

**** Significant statistical difference**

Figure (1) represents that, the majority (83.7%) had satisfactory level of knowledge regarding safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis post intervention compared to 16.3% pre intervention. While 93.7% had unsatisfactory level of knowledge at per intervention with statistical significant difference, this reflects marked improvement in nurses' knowledge post intervention.

Table (3): Distribution of studied nurses' total knowledge regarding hemodialysis and its safety measures (n=80)

Total knowledge	Pre intervention		Post Intervention		Statistical test	
	N	%	N	%	χ^2	Sig
Total General Knowledge					66.66	0.000**
Unsatisfactory	75	93.7	25	31.3		
Satisfactory	5	6.3	55	68.8		
Total care and preparation					106.03	0.000**
Unsatisfactory	70	87.5	5	6.3		
Satisfactory	10	12.5	75	93.7		
Total steps of preparation for children undergoing hemodialysis					126.04	0.000**
Unsatisfactory	75	93.7	4	5		
Satisfactory	5	6.3	76	95		
Total safety measures					58.52	0.000**
Unsatisfactory	73	91.2	26	32.5		
Satisfactory	7	8.8	54	67.5		

Table (3) reveals that there was a statistically significant difference between pre and post intervention among studied nurses' total knowledge regarding hemodialysis and its safety, the more than two thirds (68.8%) of studied nurse had satisfactory knowledge about the hemodialysis at post intervention compared to 6.3% of them pre intervention. Concerning total care and preparation of hemodialysis, most of them (93.7%) had satisfactory knowledge post intervention compared to 12.5% of them pre intervention. In addition, the most (95%) of the studied nurses had satisfactory knowledge post intervention regarding total steps of preparation also regarding total safety measures more than two thirds (67.5) of nurses had satisfactory knowledge post intervention compared to 8.8% of them pre intervention.

Table (4): Number and percentage distribution of studied nurses' practice regarding application of guidelines for management of children before hemodialysis pre and post intervention (n=80).

Practice	Pre Intervention Done		Post Intervention Done		Statistical test	
	N	%	N	%	χ^2	Sig
Preparation of the children						
Measuring body weight	30	37.5	77	96.3	62.32	0.000**
Measuring temperature	21	26.3	78	97.5	86.08	0.000**
Measuring pulse	24	30	76	95	72.10	0.000**
Measuring respiration	32	40	78	97.5	61.55	0.000**
Measuring blood pressure	13	16.3	79	98.7	111.40	0.000**
Assessing access site for signs of infection	18	22.5	76	95	86.75	0.000**
Preparation of the hemodialysis machine						
Priming all lines and the dialyzer with the prescribed solution	3	3.7	74	92.5	126.20	0.000**
Checking the dialyzer and circuit for air bubbles	5	6.3	76	95	126.04	0.000**
Setting the dialysate flow	15	18.8	77	96.3	98.31	0.000**
Setting heparin time and infusion rate	32	40	78	97.5	61.55	0.000**
Setting session length	31	38.8	77	96.3	60.28	0.000**
Setting the blood pump at (150-200) m/ml	30	37.5	75	93.8	56.10	0.000**

Total Preparation of the hemodialysis machine (Competent)	3	3.7	74	92.5	126.20	0.000**
Total Preparation of the children (Competent)	5	6.3	76	95	126.04	0.000**
Initiation of the hemodialysis procedure						
Cleansing each catheter exit with 70% alcohol or 10% povidone iodine	19	23.8	71	88.8	68.67	0.000**
Unclamping catheters and with hemodialysis raw injected heparin from them	18	22.5	73	91.3	77.08	0.000**
Priming each catheter with 10 ml normal saline 0.9%.	19	23.8	75	93.8	80.87	0.000**
Connecting the blood lines to each catheter	21	26.3	73	91.3	69.73	0.000**
Total Initiation of the hemodialysis procedure (Competent)	4	5	70	87.5	109.51	0.000**
Total practice of application of guidelines(Competent)	1	1.3	71	88.8	123.73	0.000**

** Statistical significance difference

Table (4): illustrates that there was a statistically significant difference pre and post intervention with marked improvement regarding to studied nurses' application of guidelines for management of children before hemodialysis. It shows that most of studied nurses (97.5%) had measuring the child' temperature and respiration respectively post intervention compared to 26.3% & 40% pre intervention. Regarding preparation of the hemodialysis machine this table found that (93.8%) of nurses had setting the blood pump at (150-200) m/ml post intervention compared to 37.5% pre intervention. Furthermore, initiation of the hemodialysis procedure, it shows that most of them (93.8%) had priming each catheter with 10 ml normal saline 0.9% post intervention compared to 23.8% pre intervention.

Table (5): Distribution of studied nurses according to high-flux and low-flux membranes of children undergoing hemodialysis pre and post intervention (n=80).

Practice	Pre Intervention Done		Post Intervention Done		Statistical test	
	N	%	N	%	χ^2	Sig
Hemodialysis membrane and fluxes						
Use high- flux membrane as doctor prescription	3	3.8	64	80	95.54	0.000**
Set an option in the machine to continuous blood volume monitoring during the session.	7	8.8	61	76.3	74.57	0.000**
Total Hemodialysis membrane and fluxes(Competent)	2	2.5	62	77.5	93.75	0.000**
Hemodialysis time and frequency						
Set the dialysis session time for three to four hours according to patient condition and doctor order	20	25	68	85	58.18	0.000**
The nurse informs the parents of children about frequency of hemodialysis sessions per week	16	20	70	87.5	73.31	0.000**
Total Hemodialysis time and frequency(Competent)	18	22.5	67	83.8	60.26	0.000**
Implementing hemodialysis filtration in hemodialysis unit						
Ultra-filtration applied for dialysis session	18	22.5	74	92.5	80.20	0.000**
Do not add isolated ultra-filtration time to the session length.	17	21.3	65	81.3	57.63	0.000**
Total Implementing hemodialysis filtration in hemodialysis unit (Competent)	16	20	70	87.5	73.31	0.000**
Guidelines safety measures for hemodynamic instability during hemodialysis						

Strict monitoring of fluid/nutritional intake	18	22.5	62	77.5	48.40	0.000**
Lower limb pneumatic compression	10	12.5	61	76.3	65.85	0.000**
Avoiding a rapid drop in plasma volume	17	21.3	66	82.5	60.11	0.000**
Administer medications as an agonist	27	33.8	63	78.8	32.91	0.000**
Total Guidelines safety measures for hemodynamic instability (Competent)	10	12.5	62	77.5	68.28	0.000**
Total High-flux and low-flux membranes (Competent)	5	6.3	60	75	78.38	0.000**

Table (5): reflects that there was a statistically significant difference pre and post intervention with marked improvement regarding to studied nurses' practice regarding high-flux and low-flux membranes of children undergoing hemodialysis. It shows that the majority (80%) of studied nurses had use high-flux membrane post intervention compared to 3.8% pre intervention. Regarding hemodialysis time and frequency this table cleared that 87.5% of studied nurses inform the parents about frequency of hemodialysis sessions/week post intervention compared to 20% pre intervention. Concerning implementing hemodialysis filtration in hemodialysis unit, the result clear that 92.5% of nurses had applied ultra-filtration for dialysis session Moreover, the total guidelines safety measures for hemodynamic instability during hemodialysis was more than three quarter (77.5%) of nurses using safety guideline post intervention compared to 12.5% pre intervention.

Table (6): Distribution of studied nurses' practice after hemodialysis pre and post intervention (n=80).

Practice	Pre Intervention Done		Post Intervention Done		Statistical test	
	N	%	N	%	χ^2	Sig
I. Termination of procedure as regards children						
Connecting prescribed solution to the blood lines	2	2.5	65	81.3	101.91	0.000**
Turning on solution to return blood to children through arterial line	4	5	77	96.3	133.24	0.000**
Turning on blood pump to return blood to children through venous line	32	40	59	73.8	18.57	0.000**
Disinfecting the catheter moving from the hub toward the body	32	40	50	62.5	8.10	0.004**
Disconnecting the blood line from the catheter	20	25	46	57.5	17.43	0.000**
Flushing the lumens of the catheters with 10ml of normal saline 0.9%	28	35	52	65	14.40	0.000**
Instilling heparin into each catheter	23	28.7	62	77.5	38.17	0.000**
Measuring temperature	21	26.3	75	93.8	75.93	0.000**
Measuring pulse	24	30	72	90	60.00	0.000**
Measuring respiration	20	25	61	76.3	42.03	0.000**
Measuring blood pressure	24	30	65	81.3	42.56	0.000**
Measuring body weight	31	38.8	64	80	28.21	0.000**
Total Termination of procedure as regards children (Competent)	8	10	65	81.3	81.85	0.000**
II. Termination of procedure as regards machine						
Disconnecting the used blood tubing and dialyzer from dialysis machine	14	17.5	76	95	97.62	0.000**

Cleansing outer surface of machine with a bleach solution	13	16.3	77	96.3	104.02	0.000**
Performing chemical disinfection using citric acid after each session	23	28.7	76	95	74.42	0.000**
Total Termination of procedure as regards machine (Competent)	11	13.8	76	95	106.44	0.000**
Total performance after hemodialysis (Competent)	18	22.5	74	92.5	80.20	0.000**

Table (6): reflects that there was a statistically significant difference pre and post intervention with marked improvement regarding to studied nurses' practice regarding practice after hemodialysis. Regarding termination of procedure as regards children this table shows that the majority (96.3%) of studied nurses had Turning on solution to return blood to children through arterial line post intervention compared to 5% pre intervention. Concerning, termination of procedure as regards machine this table found that 95% of studied nurses cleansing outer surface of machine with a bleach solution post intervention compared to 16.3% pre intervention. Moreover, the total performance after hemodialysis was the majority (92.5%) of nurses had competent practice post intervention compared to 22.5% pre intervention.

Table (7): Distribution of Studied nurses according to policy of infection control for children on maintenance hemodialysis pre and post intervention (n=80).

Practice	Pre Intervention Done		Post Intervention Done		Statistical test	
	N	%	N	%	χ^2	Sig
Before the initiation of hemodialysis procedure						
Washing hands	16	20	61	76.3	50.69	0.000**
Wearing sterile gloves	8	10	55	68.8	57.83	0.000**
Wearing plastic apron	27	33.8	58	72.5	24.11	0.000**
Wearing face shield	17	21.3	78	97.5	96.41	0.000**
During the hemodialysis procedure						
Washing hands before any contact with children	18	22.5	67	83.8	60.26	0.000**
Changing sterile gloves between children	25	31.3	79	98.7	80.11	0.000**
Wearing plastic apron before any contact with children	9	11.3	62	77.5	71.12	0.000**
Wearing face shield before any contact with children	10	12.5	62	77.5	68.28	0.000**
After the hemodialysis procedure						
Washing hands after terminating procedure	8	10	60	75	69.15	0.000**
Washing hands after removal of gloves	4	5	59	73.8	79.20	0.000**
Wearing sterile gloves before terminating procedure	5	6.3	58	72.5	73.54	0.000**
Wearing plastic apron before terminating procedure	5	6.3	58	72.5	73.54	0.000**
Wearing face shield before terminating procedure	4	5	59	73.8	79.20	0.000**
Total Policy of infection control	13	16.3	68	85	75.63	0.000**

Table (7): illustrates that there was a statistically significant difference pre and post intervention with marked improvement regarding to studied nurses about policy of infection control for children on maintenance hemodialysis. Before the initiation of hemodialysis procedure it shows 76.3% & 68.8% respectively of studied nurses had washing hands and wearing sterile gloves post intervention compared to 20% & 10% pre intervention. Regarding procedure during the hemodialysis this table found that 98.7% of nurses had changing sterile gloves between children post intervention compared to 31.3% pre intervention. Also, after procedure of hemodialysis this table shows that 75% of nurses

had Washing hands after terminating procedure post intervention compared to 10% pre intervention. Furthermore, total policy of infection control (85%) of nurses had competent practice post intervention compared to 16.3% pre intervention.

Figure (2): Percentage distribution of studied nurses according to total practice about intervention for application of safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis pre and post intervention (n=80).

** significant statistical difference

Figure (2) Concerning the studied nurses' total practice regarding application of safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis, this figure reveals that, there was a marked improvement in nurses' practice after implementation of training program with a statistically significant difference ($P = 0.000$). Whereas most (81.2%) of the studied nurses had competent total practice post implementation of training program in compared to only (8.8%) pre implementation.

Table (8): Correlation between total nurses knowledge and their total practices safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis pre- and post-intervention (n=80).

Items	Spearman correlation	Practice pre	Practice post
Knowledge	r	.216	.590**
	P value	.054	.000

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table (8): reveals that, there were strong positive correlation between the studied nurses' total knowledge and their total practice about safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis post intervention at $r = .590$ ($p < 0.01$). While, negative correlation between the studied nurses' total knowledge and their total practice pre intervention at $r = .216$ ($p = .054$).

DISCUSSION

Regarding to characteristics of studied nurses the current study results revealed that, more than one third of the studied nurses' age ranged between 20 to less than 30 years with mean age 31.49 ± 4.621 , These findings are congruent with those reported by **Eslam et al. (2020)** in a study about "Effect of Implementing Evidence Based Nursing Guidelines on Nurses' Performance about Care Provided for Children Undergoing Hemodialysis", Egypt who mentioned more than half of the studied nurses were aged between 20 to 30 years with the mean age score 28.6 ± 5.69 years and the majority of them were

females. Also disagree with **Bayoumi & Mahmoud (2017)** who studied "Effect of Education Program on Nurses' Knowledge and Practice Regarding Care of Central Venous Line in Pediatric hemodialysis" reported that one third of the nurses were aged more than 30 years. The results of the current study revealed that approximately two thirds of them were female. From the researcher point of view, this may be related to the studying of nursing in Egyptian universities were exclusive for females only till few years ago.

In relation to the nurses' qualification, the current study revealed that slightly less than half of the studied nurses had nursing bachelor in nursing science certificate; while the minority of them had nursing diploma. This is in consistence with **Ibrahim et al. (2019)** who studied "nurses' performance regarding care of children undergoing hemodialysis" and their results found that about three quarters had nursing diploma while the minority had nursing bachelors. On the other hand, this results incongruent with **Ahamed & Sallam (2018)** who reported that more than half of the nurses had nursing bachelor.

Regarding to years of experience of the studied nurses, the result of current study showed slightly that less than half of the studied nurses were from ten to fifteen years of experience. This is corresponding with the finding of **Eslam et al. (2020)** and his results showed that more than one third of them had 5 - <10 years of experience. From the researcher point of view, this may be due to most of studied nurses were recently graduated.

Regarding the attendance of the previous training program in hemodialysis, the current study found that the majority of nurses were received training courses. This may be abundant of finances to support ongoing education. This is supported by **Eid, & Abdel Aziz (2017)** who studied "Proposed Developed Standards: Staff Nurses Compliance at Dialysis Unit" and portrayed that the majority of nurses hadn't attending staff development program in hospital. Similarly this result was in agreement with **Koren (2016)** who studied "Hospital environmental services, policy and procedure the compendium of standards of practice for nurses" in Egypt, and reported aware of nurses increase quality improvement, nurses had attended conference during the past 5 years and attended educational lectures. From the researcher point of view; in-service education and staff development in hospitals are positive effect on improving and monitoring the quality of nursing care provided for children with hemodialysis. Also, other reasons might be work overload, shortage of staff, lack of nurses' incentives to improve their knowledge and lack of desire to update knowledge especially whom working in critical units for several years. Moreover, the workload and supportive learning environment could be barriers to accessing sources of education for hemodialysis nurses.

As regards nurses' knowledge related to hemodialysis the current study showed that , the majority of studied nurses had correct answer post intervention about concept and indications of hemodialysis compared to one third of them in pre intervention with highly statistically significant difference between the studied nurses throughout the intervention. This was in agreement with **Besely et al. (2018)** who studied in title "Effect of implementing health education program for nurses on satisfaction level of patients undergoing Hemodialysis" Egypt and reported that three quarter of the studied nurses had total unsatisfactory response in their scores of knowledge about meaning and indication of hemodialysis pre-program implementation. It also exhibited that 95% of them had satisfactory level of their scores of knowledge immediately post educational program implementation.

The current study mentioned that, there was a highly statistically significant difference between the studied nurses regarding their knowledge concerning complications of hemodialysis throughout the application of safety measure intervention. This finding is similar to the results of **Sarika (2017)** who studied "Assessment of knowledge and practices of parents regarding home management of children with chronic hemodialysis " in India and stated that, drop of blood pressure musculoskeletal

complications are the most common occurring for the patients during hemodialysis as a result of hyponatrimia or due to hypo-osmolality.

Many studies search in this line in Egypt and other country for instance, **Saleh et al. (2018)**, who studied "Nurses compliance to standards of nursing care for hemodialysis patients: Educational and training intervention" in Egypt who found that the majority of studied nurses had good knowledge after implementation with highly statistically significant difference before and three weeks after implementing the evidence-based nursing guidelines. **Tobin & Girotra (2019)** stated that the nurses must educated about the complication of hemodialysis such as cardiovascular, nutritional, gastrointestinal, hepatic, endocrinal, complications of arteriovenous fistula (AV), infections, nervous system and sleep disorders. Also, study done by **Ball (2016)** entitled "The button hole technique: Strategies to reduce infections" who pointed out that failure to follow-up the fistula continually leads to increased infection". These findings suggest that there are structural barriers in the unit, including lack of documentation forms to meet standards of care. From the researcher point of view; pediatric nurses can help by involving the pediatric patient suffering from chronic kidney disease as much as possible in their health care decision, informing them of all treatment options and placing an emphasis on self-care

As regard the total knowledge of the studied nurses about intervention for application of safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis, the current work showed that there was there was a marked improvement in nurses' knowledge after implementation of training program with a highly statistical significant difference between the studied nurses throughout the intervention. The result of the current study could be attributed to continuous supervision from the head nurse of the hemodialysis unit. This was approved by the study of **Hassan et al. (2017)** who studied "Assessment of Nurses' Application of Guidelines for Management of Children Undergoing Hemodialysis" and reported that the majority of nurses had good total score of knowledge with highly statistically significant difference in total knowledge scores of the studied nurses, where p-value=0.000 related to care of children undergoing hemodialysis.

In addition, **Saleh (2019)** studied that "Nurses Compliance to Standards of Nursing Care for Hemodialysis Patients: Educational and Training Intervention" and found that there were increasing percent in nurses achieved very good and excellent overall total knowledge in the post-test and the follow-up compared with the pre-test periods and concluded that, structured interventions for education and training are essential for the nursing care for hemodialysis patients and lead to nursing staff to provide a strong performance. This could be due to the comprehensive content of the educational training program, its relevance to the field of hemodialysis, the written booklet of the program, which serves as an ongoing reference and may be that changes in practice based on the guidelines standards of care and the Egyptian guidelines for hemodialysis nurses also contribute to improvement their total knowledge scores.

Concerning the studied nurses regarding the application of safety measure for management of children before hemodialysis, the current study mentioned that, there was a highly statistically significant difference marked improvement regarding to studied nurses' application of guidelines for **management of children before** hemodialysis. Also, the majority of them had competent practice post regarding preparation of the hemodialysis machine, and initiation of the hemodialysis procedure respectively compared to only small number pre implementation of training program. Moreover, this table shows that majority of studied nurses had competent practice post implementation throughout training intervention. This was in agreement with **Ahmed (2017)**, who conducted a study entitled "Assessment of Nursing Care Provided for Children undergoing Hemodialysis." revealed that, all studied nurses primed lines and dialyzer with prescribed solution, set dialysate flow, heparin infusion time and rate, session length as well as blood pump post implementation.

In addition, another study done by **Ibrahim et al. (2019)** who reported that the majority of the nurses had competent practice level regarding measuring blood pressure before, during and after hemodialysis post program implementation. Other preparation reported by **Abdalmajed (2017)** entitled "Nurses' Knowledge and Practice Regarding Nursing Care of Hemodialysis Catheter in Pediatric Renal Units" in Khartoum were including the majority of nurses assessed the catheters for infection before initiating hemodialysis, cleansed catheters exit with 70% alcohol or 10% povidone iodine, injected heparin into catheters after terminating hemodialysis. These findings could be related to nurses' awareness that keeping access site patent and infection free ensures that hemodialysis will go smoothly without complications.

As regards the studied nurses' practices concerning to use high-flux dialyzers for children with minimal residual function, the current work showed that, the majority of studied nurses had competent practices post hemodialysis time and frequency, implementing hemodialysis filtration in hemodialysis unit, and guidelines safety measures for hemodynamic instability post implementation with marked improvement, more than three quarter of them had competent post application of safety measure. These results was agreed with **Yousef et al. (2019)** who supporting these findings entitled " The effect of nursing educational program on knowledge and practice of nurses regarding infection control measures for children under hemodialysis" and stated that, the most common studied nurses assess the vascular function and use high-flux dialyzers for children with minimal residual function and monitor the blood volume on the machine. Also, access time used for session within 4 hours. **The American Academy of pediatrics (2018)** considers that the children with a fistula have the fewest complications, compared to all other access choices. The fistula is considered the "gold standard" access because it has a lower risk of infections, lower risk of forming clots, performs better than other accesses, allows for greater blood flow, lasts longer than the other access types, can last many years. In addition, most children put on arteriovenous fistula, which had fewer complications, and attending three sessions per week which is the typical prescription for patients on hemodialysis to allow better control of blood pressure which controls the survival rate.

The present study revealed that all nurses prepared hemodialysis machine according to guidelines. This could be attributed to that the machine is considered the core of hemodialysis procedure and without its preparation, no hemodialysis could be delivered. This result is consistent with the result of **Ahmed (2017)** who found that all nurses attained good score in the preparation of hemodialysis machine.

It was found from the current study receiving application of safety measure intervention. that most of studied nurses in their observations during the session of hemodialysis measured temperature, pulse, respiration, blood pressure, clotting time/ hour line connection, prescribed medication as heparin & iron and observe also the complication during intradialytic. These findings could be due to the nurses' awareness about the occurrence of intradialytic complications as hypotension, palpitation, fever and dyspnea.

These findings were in the same line with the findings of **Ibrahim et al. (2019)** who reported that the majority of the nurses had competent practice level regarding measuring vital signs during intradialytic. The researcher believes that measuring vital signs accurately for children undergoing hemodialysis is very important to indicate any abnormality or health problems during period of hemodialysis. Moreover, **Khamis et al. (2022)** supported the current study by studied "Assessment of safety measures in hemodialysis units" who stated that, the majority of studied nurses were assess the musculoskeletal complications because it is the most common occurring for the patients during hemodialysis as a result of hyponatremia or due to hypo-osmolality.

Concerning the nurses' practices in relation to managing suboptimal dialysis adequacy of children undergoing hemodialysis, the current study illustrated that, there was a highly statistical significant between nurses' practice pre and post program intervention. These findings were supported by **(Hassan et al., 2021)** who revealed that participant's nurses prepared hemodialysis machine and vascular function assessment, this could be attributed to that the machine and child assessing is essential for the procedure.

As regards the relation between total knowledge of studied nurses and their characteristics about safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis, the current study pointed that, There statistically significant relation between characteristics of the studied nurses and their total knowledge about safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis pre-intervention. While, highly statistically significant relation between training program in hemodialysis of the studied nurses and their total knowledge about safety measures for children undergoing hemodialysis post-intervention with p value (≤ 0.01), it shows that the trained nurses had highest mean of knowledge.

These results were congruent with **Marquis & Huston (2017)** they showed that, there was reached to statistical significant correlation between nurses' knowledge regarding hemodialysis and their characteristic in the name of qualification, residence as nurses' knowledge was increased with age from 30 to 39 years old. The researcher suggested that continuous education to nurses and health workers to improve their knowledge and perform all the skills needed and full supervision of the dialysis process from the start to the end of session.

Related to total score of the nurses' practices about intervention for application of safety measures for children undergoing Hemodialysis , all of the nurses had achieved competent in total practices about preparing patients, equipment and machines with significant competent in nurses' practices post intervention. These findings may be due to effectiveness of the application of safety measures. Despite no new policies were implemented in the unit during the study time. Accordingly, this improvement in the nurses' practices was related to the effect of the intervention. This result supported by **Kazley et al. (2018)** they stated that good practice is the result of theoretical understanding that helps nurses to acquire new skills and practice.

In the same respect, **Kimmel & Rosenberg (2020)** reflected that the importance of receiving accurate and timely training by skill lead to improvement the nurses' practices. Lastly, the present study results showed that there was a strong positive correlation between nurses' total knowledge & their practices were dedicated in the posttests at ($P < 0.01$). This strong positive relationship suggests knowledge and performance were related in this study. These may be due to the effect of the application safety measures educational and training intervention, effort by nurses by attending our program. In the same line, **Salah et al. (2018)** found that there was positive correlation between nurse's knowledge and their performance i.e.. Increase in knowledge scores matches, also increase in practice scores. While, disagreed with **Ibrahim et al. (2019)** who concluded that the relationship between the participants knowledge scores and their practice scores was not dedicated in the pre and post periods of the study.

CONCLUSION

In the light of the study results, it was concluded that knowledge and practices of the studied nurses were improved after implementation of the intervention guidelines. In this context, there was a marked improvement of total satisfactory knowledge and competent practice which reflect satisfactory significant difference pre-post guidelines implementation. Moreover, there is a statistically significant relation between nurses' knowledge and their practice.

Recommendation:

- Periodic training programs and refreshing courses should be provided to nurses to enhance to use safety measures, which will reflect into their performance and minimize the risk for transmission of infection.
- Continuing education programs on regular basis is suggested in order to refresh and update nurse's practice.
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